

Influence of anisotropic elasticity on the mechanical properties of fivefold twinned nanowires

Florian Niekel^a, Erdmann Spiecker^a, Erik Bitzek^{a,*}

^a*Department of Material Science and Engineering, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU), 91058 Erlangen, Germany*

Abstract

Previous atomistic simulations and experiments have shown an increased Young's modulus and yield strength of fivefold twinned (FT) face-centered cubic metal nanowires (NWs) when compared to single crystalline (SC) NWs of the same orientation. Here we report the results of atomistic simulations of SC and FT Ag, Al, Au, Cu and Ni NWs with diameters between 2 and 50 nm under tension and compression. The simulations show that the differences in Young's modulus between SC and FTNWs are correlated with the elastic anisotropy of the metal, with Al showing a decreased Young's modulus. We develop a simple analytical model based on disclination theory and constraint anisotropic elasticity to explain the trend in the difference of the Young's modulus between SC and FTNWs. Taking into account the role of surface stresses and the elastic properties of twin boundaries allows to account for the observed size effect in Young's modulus. The model furthermore explains the different relative yield strengths in tension and compression as well as the material and loading dependent failure mechanisms in FTNWs.

Keywords: Fivefold twinning, Numerical algorithms (C), Anisotropic material (B), Microstructures (A), Strengthening and mechanisms (A)

*Corresponding author. Address: Department of Material Science and Engineering, Intitute I, Martensstr. 5, 91058 Erlangen, Germany. Tel.: +49 9131 8527507, fax.: +49 9131 8527504.
Email address: erik.bitzek@fau.de (Erik Bitzek)

1. Introduction

Metallic nanostructures have recently attracted a lot of interest due to their remarkable mechanical properties. Nanometer sized pillars, thin films, particles, rods or whiskers for example can show strengths which are significantly larger than those of the bulk material, often reaching values close to the computed theoretical values (Greer and Hosson, 2011; Kraft et al., 2010; Zhu and Li, 2010). Furthermore, the elastic response of nano sized structures was also reported to be different from the bulk behavior (Chen et al., 2012; Liang et al., 2005; McDowell et al., 2008b). These differences are generally attributed to the absence of defects like dislocations and flaws and the high surface to volume ratio (Chen et al., 2012; Greer and Hosson, 2011; Kraft et al., 2010; Liang et al., 2005; McDowell et al., 2008b; Weinberger and Cai, 2012; Zhu and Li, 2010). Together, these effects can lead to changes in the dominant deformation mode, e.g., from dislocation mediated plasticity to deformation twinning (Amodeo et al., 2014; Lee et al., 2014; Oh et al., 2007; Sedlmayr et al., 2012).

Currently, nanostructures in which five twin segments are joined along a common quintuple line have become the focus of many investigations (Damm et al., 2011; Filleter et al., 2012; Huang et al., 2011; Jiang et al., 2013; Lucas et al., 2008; Monk et al., 2008; Niekiet et al., 2014; Sun et al., 2013a; Zhu et al., 2012). Such fivefold twinned (FT) structures are found in various classes of materials like face-centered cubic (fcc) and body centered cubic (bcc) metals, semiconductors and alloys, forming nano particles, rods and wires (Hofmeister, 2004). Fivefold twinned silver nanowires (NWs) in particular play an important role in flexible electronics, e.g., as transparent electrodes in organic light emitting diodes or printed solar cells (Garnett et al., 2012; Hu et al., 2010; Krantz et al., 2011, 2012; Lee et al., 2008; Lim et al., 2012). The functionality and reliability in such applications depend critically on the mechanical properties of the NW network. In this context knowledge about the mechanical properties of fivefold twinned nanowires (FTNWs) is of fundamental importance, in particular as their properties are significantly different from their single crystalline (SC) counterparts. An increased stiffness and yield strength were for example reported in tension (Filleter et al., 2012; Zhu et al., 2012), bending (Jing et al., 2006; Wu et al., 2005, 2006) and

nanindentation experiments (Lucas et al., 2008). Many atomistic simulations were carried out on various elements to elucidate the underlying reasons for these improved properties (Cao and Wei, 2006; Filletier et al., 2012; Gao et al., 2012; Leach et al., 2007; McDowell et al., 2008b; Sun et al., 2013a; Wen et al., 2012; Wu et al., 2011; Yoo et al., 2010; Zheng et al., 2014). A systematic study comparing different fcc metals over a wide range of diameters is however lacking, and no consensus has been reached on the underlying reasons for the changes in elastic properties and the yield stress.

Here we present the result of atomistic studies of SC and FT Al, Ni, Cu, Ag and Au NWs spanning diameters from 2 to 50 nm. The results are captured in a simple but comprehensive model based on constraints due to the FT structure and anisotropic elasticity. It is able to explain the differences in elastic and plastic response as well as failure mechanisms with respect to single crystalline wires, and the trends for different fcc metals.

The paper is structured as follows: first we review the literature on FTNWs, focusing on their morphology and its description in terms of disclinations and on their mechanical properties. Then we present the methodology and the results of the simulations. We then propose a simple analytical model for the change in stress state of FTNWs under uniaxial load and its dependence on the elastic anisotropy. We use this model to discuss the simulation results and their relationship to experiments and to provide an outlook for the use of FT structures in the context of strain engineering. We close with a summary.

2. Morphology and mechanical properties of fivefold twinned nanowires

2.1. Morphology and strain state

FTNWs consist of five wedge shaped segments joined by $\{111\}$ -twin boundaries and sharing a common $[101]$ -direction along the wire axis. An idealized structure of a FTNW is shown in figure 1a), where also the coordinate system used throughout this work to describe a twin segment is introduced. Such pentagonal shaped wires with $\{100\}$ surfaces are also observed in the experiments, however with more rounded edges (Chen et al., 2004a,b; Gao et al., 2005; Ni et al., 2005; Reyes-Gasga et al., 2006), but also round wires are frequently

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of a) the microstructure of fivefold twinned NWs and b) the compensation of the 7.53° misfit by a positive partial wedge disclination ω at the quintuple line, a Cartesian coordinate system and respective crystallographic directions are drawn for the highlighted segment, c) illustration of sample geometry in simulations: cross sectional view of FT and SCNW indicating definition of diameter d , colored according to coordination number.

found (Chen et al., 2004a; Lim et al., 2012; Wu et al., 2006). Joining five wedge shaped segments of fcc crystal structure by $\{111\}$ -twin boundaries would lead to a gap of 7.35° , as the angle between two $\{111\}$ -planes in cubic systems is 70.53° (see figure 1b)). FT structures therefore are inherently strained to avoid this gap. As pointed out by De Wit (1972) the closure of this gap can be described as a positive partial wedge disclination with its Frank vector $\vec{\omega}$ along the center line of the NW and its magnitude $\omega = 7.35^\circ$, as schematically shown in figure 1b). The stress field produced by a wedge disclination with $\vec{\omega}$ parallel to the axis \vec{z} of a cylinder with radius R can be derived using isotropic linear elasticity and cylindrical coordinates to (Romanov and Vladimirov, 1992):

$$\sigma_{rr}(r, \theta) = D \ln \left(\frac{r}{R} \right), \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_{\theta\theta}(r, \theta) = D \left[\ln \left(\frac{r}{R} \right) + 1 \right], \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{zz}(x, y) = \nu D \left[2 \ln \left(\frac{r}{R} \right) + 1 \right], \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_{r\theta} = \sigma_{rz} = \sigma_{\theta z} = 0, \quad (4)$$

with $D = \omega\mu(1 + \nu)/2\pi$, where the shear modulus is denoted by μ and the Poisson's ratio by ν . Johnson et al. (2007) were able to visualize the strain field in a FT Au nanoparticle by strain mapping of a high resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) image which corresponds to the strain field of a central disclination. Recently it was shown by directly comparing experimental X-ray diffraction data with atomistic calculations that the complex strain field in Ag FTNW could indeed be explained by the presence of a central disclination (Niekiet et al., 2014). Disclination theory has furthermore been used to address the stability and relaxation mechanisms (Gryaznov et al., 1999; Kolesnikova and Romanov, 2007; Romanov et al., 1993) in FT structures as well as their growth mechanisms (Yasnikov and Vikarchuk, 2007).

2.2. Elastic properties

Due to their small size, FTNWs are expected to show a similar increase in their Young's moduli with decreasing diameter as their SC counterparts (Diao et al., 2004; Dingreville

et al., 2005; Liang et al., 2005; McDowell et al., 2008b; Miller and Shenoy, 2000; Shankar and King, 2007). Currently, two models for the size effect are discussed: effects due to the different structure at the surface (Diao et al., 2004; Dingreville et al., 2005; Miller and Shenoy, 2000) and effects due to nonlinear elasticity resulting from a prestrain of the NWs caused by the surface tension (Liang et al., 2005; Shankar and King, 2007). As pointed out by McDowell et al. (2008b), experiments show a size effect at much larger diameters than in atomistic simulations, indicating that other effects like the presence of surface layers, e.g. oxides, have to be taken into account to explain the increased Young’s moduli in experiments.

Whether the elastic response of FTNWs differs from SCNWs with the same crystallographic orientation and diameter is currently under debate. Zhu et al. (2012) performed *in situ* tensile tests in a scanning electron microscope (SEM) on Ag FTNWs with diameters between 34 and 130 nm and found an increase in Young’s modulus compared to bulk Ag with the same crystallographic orientation ($E_{[101]}^{\text{free}} = 83.8$ GPa, see Tab.1) for diameters below 80 nm, with the highest Young’s modulus $E = 176$ GPa for a wire of diameter $d = 34$ nm. Similarly, Filleter et al. (2012) performed *in situ* tensile test in a transmission electron microscope (TEM) on Ag FTNWs with diameters ranging from 40 to 120 nm. They also found an increase of the Young’s modulus for wires smaller than 55 nm, with the highest Young’s modulus $E = 127 \pm 4$ GPa for the smallest nanowire ($d = 41.7$ nm). Using atomic force microscopy (AFM) bending tests Wu et al. (2006) found an average Young’s Modulus of 102 ± 23 GPa for Ag FTNWs with diameters between 22 and 46 nm, which was however independent of the diameter. In all cases the FTNWs Young’s moduli were not directly compared to SCNWs. A comparison with data for the Young’s moduli of Ag SCNWs ($d = 20 - 140$ nm) obtained by Jing et al. (2006) using AFM bending test is not conclusive because of the large scatter in the data (see McDowell et al. (2008b) for a direct comparison of these data sets).

Molecular static (MS) simulations of McDowell et al. (2008b) on $\{110\}$ -oriented Ag wires showed no significant effect of the FT nanostructure on the Young’s modulus for wires with diameters below 7 nm. This is in contrast to the MS simulations by Yoo et al. (2010) on Ag and Cu FTNWs ($d = 2 - 21$ nm) which showed an enhanced Young’s modulus for FTNWs

compared to SCNWs. The magnitude of this effect was however dependent on the used atomic interaction potential. Yoo et al. (2010) attribute the increase in Young's modulus of FTNWs compared to the SCNWs to the compressional stress state at the center of FTNWs. Wu et al. (2011) come to a similar conclusion from their MD simulations on fcc Fe FTNWs who add that the central region of the NW not only behaves stiffer but even expands laterally under longitudinal load. A generally increased Young's modulus of FTNWs in comparison to SCNWs was also reported in simulations by Wen et al. (2012) for Pt, Au, Ag, Cu, Ni and Pd for NWs with a diameter of 4 nm, and for Ag FTNW of $d = 10$ nm diameter by Sun et al. (2013b). Recently, Zheng et al. (2014) found in their MS simulations on Cu FTNW with diameters ranging from $d = 6$ to 160 nm not only a similar increase of the Young's modulus with decreasing diameter, but in addition for wire diameters larger than 80 nm a nearly constant, increased Young's modulus of about 1.1 times the Young's modulus of SC Cu in the same orientation. Although the size-dependent increase of E could be nicely fitted with an empirical core-shell model, the reason for the size-independent increase of the Young's modulus remains unclear.

2.3. Yield stress and plastic deformation

It is well known that the yield stress of metallic structures like pillars, thin films, particles, rods or wires increases when their characteristic size is in the sub-micron range (Greer and Hosson, 2011; Kraft et al., 2010; Weinberger and Cai, 2012). This "smaller is stronger" effect has been attributed to the absence of pre-existing dislocations, truncation of dislocation sources, dislocation source exhaustion, dislocation starvation and dislocation nucleation-controlled plasticity (Greer and Hosson, 2011; Kraft et al., 2010; Weinberger and Cai, 2012). The same mechanisms can be expected to be at work in FTNWs. However, how the presence of the twin boundaries and the central disclination influences the yield stress has only recently become the focus of experimental investigations and computer simulations (Cao and Wei, 2006; Filleter et al., 2012; Gao et al., 2012; Jiang et al., 2013; Leach et al., 2007; Sun et al., 2013a,b; Wen et al., 2012; Wu et al., 2011).

Direct experimental comparison of the plastic deformation of fivefold and single crys-

talline wires is currently lacking. Wu et al. (2006) performed bending tests on Ag FTNWs with diameters between 10 and 15 nm before and after annealing using AFM. They report super elastic behavior followed by brittle failure for the as prepared samples, whereas the thermally annealed wires showed a decreased yield stress and a more ductile behavior, which was attributed to the elimination of the FT structure. However, the resulting microstructure was not characterized, and the yield stress was not determined. The yield strength of Ag FTNWs under tension was recently determined by Zhu et al. (2012) using *in situ* tensile test in the SEM. For diameters between 34 and 130 nm they observed an increase in yield strength with decreasing diameter which followed a power law with an exponent of $n = -0.6$. Their highest measured yield strength of $\sigma_y^{\text{FT}} = 2.6$ GPa is close to the theoretical yield strength of $\sigma_y^{\text{theo.}} = 3.5$ GPa as calculated by density functional theory (DFT) by Ogata et al. (2004). The observed size effect was attributed to the increase in Young's modulus with decreasing diameter. After the onset of yielding they observe strain hardening, which is assigned to the presence of the FT microstructure. As the yield strain is found to scale with the surface area, it is concluded that yielding is dominated by dislocation nucleation from surface sources. In their *in situ* TEM tensile tests on Ag FTNWs, Filleter et al. (2012) also measured yield stresses around 3 GPa. However, they reported only a weak dependence of the yield stress on the wire diameter. In contrast, the stress-strain curves in their *in situ* experiments showed an interesting size-dependent strain hardening behavior, with thinner NWs showing more pronounced strain hardening than thicker NWs. Filleter *et al.* could correlate the strain hardening to the nucleation of multiple local plastic regions, in which the formation of each new plastic region required a stress increase. Their atomistic simulations allowed them to identify the formation of stacking fault decahedra (SFD) as important deformation mechanism. The growth of these SFD is then hindered by surface irregularities, requiring the nucleation of new SFDs (Filleter et al., 2012). Plastic deformation of Ag FTNWs was also studied by AFM nanoindentation on the side surfaces of the wire (Lucas et al., 2008). There, the formation of a neck and series of yielding events is observed, however, no comparison with single crystalline wires were made.

The plastic deformation of FTNWs has also been the subject of several recent atomistic

studies (Cao and Wei, 2006; Filleter et al., 2012; Gao et al., 2012; Jiang et al., 2013; Leach et al., 2007; Sun et al., 2013a,b; Wen et al., 2012; Wu et al., 2011). Higher yield stresses than for single crystalline wires were found for the FTNWs in rectangular Cu-wires with a diameter of $d = 8$ nm (Cao and Wei, 2006), round Ag-wires with $d = 7.5$ nm (Gao et al., 2012) and $d = 5, 10, 20$ nm (Sun et al., 2013a,b), pentagonal Ag-wires ($d = 1.7 - 26.8$ nm) (Leach et al., 2007), pentagonal Ag, Au, Cu, Ni, Pd and Pt wires ($d = 4$ nm) (Wen et al., 2012), as well as round fcc-Fe wires ($d = 6 - 24$ nm) (Wu et al., 2011). The observed increase in yield strength relative to the SCNWs varied for a given diameter ($d = 4$ nm) across the elements from about 9% (Au) to about 31% (Ni,Cu) (Wen et al., 2012). The yield stress σ_y^{FT} of the FTNWs as well as the ratio of σ_y^{FT} and the yield stress of the single crystalline wire σ_y^{SC} increased for decreasing wire diameters (Leach et al., 2007; Wu et al., 2011). Interestingly, Sun et al. (2013b) observed that Ag FTNWs with a diameter of $d = 20$ nm showed a lower yield strength in compression compared to SCNWs, which was attributed to the already initially existing compressive stress in the FTNW.

In contrast to SCNWs of identical crystallographic orientation, which usually under tension deform by twinning (Cao and Wei, 2006; Leach et al., 2007; Park et al., 2006; Sedlmayr et al., 2012), the FTNWs deformed by the nucleation of Shockley partial dislocations at the surfaces (Cao and Wei, 2006; Gao et al., 2012; Leach et al., 2007; Wen et al., 2012). The twin boundaries were observed to act as barriers to dislocation motion, and the plastic deformation was much more localized along the wires in the FTNWs than in the SCNWs (Cao and Wei, 2006; Gao et al., 2012; Leach et al., 2007; Wen et al., 2012). The more localized deformation lead to neck formation and pronounced decreased ductility of the FTNWs. These localized regions often consist of stacking fault or micro twin arrangements with fivefold symmetry (Filleter et al., 2012; Gao et al., 2012; Jiang et al., 2013).

Different models for the enhanced yield strength of FTNWs in comparison to SCNWs have been suggested in literature: the subdivision of the FTNWs by the twin boundaries is supposed to give rise to Hall-Petch-like hardening (Cao and Wei, 2006; Leach et al., 2007). Furthermore, the nucleation sites for dislocations were different in the FT structure than in the SCNWs, which might lead to higher activation energies, and Leach et al. (2007) pointed

out that if the yield strain would be constant, the yield strength would need to be scaled accordingly with the increased Young’s modulus.

3. Methods

To characterize the mechanical properties of FTNWs under uniaxial load, we performed quasistatic tensile tests in the elastic regime, as well as tensile tests at constant temperature and strain rate until rupture. As reference, the same simulations were performed on SCNWs. The atomic interaction was described by the embedded atom method (EAM), using the potentials of Mishin for Al (Mishin et al., 1999), Ni (Mishin, 2004), Cu (Mishin et al., 2001), Ag (Williams et al., 2006), and the potential of Park and Zimmerman (2005) for Au. The 0 K lattice constants, elastic constants and the anisotropy ratio of these potentials are provided in Tab. 1.

Table 1: Lattice constant a , Elastic constants C_{ij} and anisotropy ratio A of the used EAM potentials and derived values used in the analytical framework (see Discussion, sec. 5.2); lattice constants are given in Å, the units of elastic constants and Young’s moduli are GPa.

Element	a	C_{11}	C_{12}	C_{44}	A	$\nu_{[101]}^{[10\bar{1}]}$	$\nu_{[101]}^{[010]}$	$E_{[101]}^{\text{free}}$	$E_{[101]}^{\text{FT}}$	$\epsilon_{zz}(\omega = 0)$
Ag ^a	4.09	124.3	93.9	46.4	3.05	-0.097	0.829	83.8	88.1	0.029
Al ^b	4.05	113.7	61.5	31.6	1.21	0.265	0.398	79.9	78.0	0.191
Au ^c	4.08	186.1	157.1	39.0	2.69	0.000	0.844	78.0	78.0	0.032
Cu ^d	3.62	169.9	122.7	76.2	3.23	-0.138	0.822	131.3	141.7	0.028
Ni ^e	3.52	241.5	150.7	127.3	2.80	-0.110	0.693	226.6	239.1	0.033

^a(Williams et al., 2006)

^b(Mishin et al., 1999)

^c(Park and Zimmerman, 2005)

^d(Mishin et al., 2001)

^e(Mishin, 2004)

The geometry of the simulated $\langle 110 \rangle$ -oriented wires is shown in Fig. 1c). The SCNWs have a hexagonal cross section, with four $\{111\}$ - and two $\{100\}$ -surfaces. The pentagonal

FTNWs are bordered by five $\{100\}$ -surfaces. In the following, the diameter d of the wires is taken as the one corresponding to the largest cross sectional infitting circle, see Fig. 1c). Periodic boundary conditions (pbc) were used along the direction of the wire axis, thus simulating infinitely long NWs. The studied wires had diameters of $d = 6a$ to $122a$, (a being the lattice constant, see Tab. 1), i.e from about 2 to 50 nm. For the quasistatic simulations, the length of the simulation cell along the wire axis was $l = 71a/\sqrt{2}$. For the MD simulations at constant strain rate, wires with $d = 60a$ and $l = 432a/\sqrt{2}$ leading to an aspect ratio of about 5 were chosen. The initial configurations were relaxed using the fast inertial relaxation engine (FIRE) (Bitzek et al., 2006) while adjusting l to lead to a stress free sample.

To determine the linear elastic response of the wires under tensile loading, an iterative procedure is used. The simulation cell and all atomic positions are scaled linearly according to a strain increment of 2×10^{-6} and the energy is minimized using FIRE. The resulting configuration is scaled again, until an engineering strain of $\epsilon_{zz} = 10^{-4}$ was reached. In addition, wires with $l = 84a/\sqrt{2}$, $d = 60a$ were similarly deformed and subsequently relaxed in the range of $\epsilon_{zz} -4\%$ and 7% , using a increment of 10^{-2} .

For the simulations at constant temperature, the wires were equilibrated for 40 ps at 300 K in the microcanonical ensemble followed by 80 ps using a combined Nosé-Hoover thermostat and barostat (Hoover, 1985) to allow for stress relaxation in the longitudinal direction. Tensile deformation was prescribed by homogeneously scaling the simulation box and atomic positions at each time step, corresponding to a strain rate of 10^8 s^{-1} , while using the thermostat to keep the temperature at 300 K.

To describe the strain state in the NWs the atomic strain tensor (Shimizu et al., 2007) was used. The atomic stress tensor is calculated following the virial expression (Allen and Tildesley, 1987). The Young's modulus of the NWs was determined from the virial stress of the configuration in the longitudinal direction at the different states of longitudinal strain. By fitting 3rd order polynomials to the extracted stress-strain response the Young's modulus is calculated as the coefficient of the linear term. The volume used in the calculation of the virial stress was taken as the product of length l and the cross sectional area A . The latter

was defined as the sum over the area of each atom in the cross sectional plane. The area per atom was calculated for each atom by modifying the bulk equilibrium area per atom in a $\{110\}$ -plane with the local atomic strain state. For situations in which many atoms are subjected to large strains, as e.g., in the case of NWs with small diameters, this correction provides significant improvement over the assumption of a constant cross sectional area per atom. The difference in total cross sectional area however becomes negligible for NWs with larger diameters. This definition of the cross section area was also used to calculate the stress-strain curves from the virial stresses of the simulation box. The images of atomistic configurations in this work were created with AtomEye (Li, 2003) and ParaView (Sandia National Laboratory et al., 2000-2008).

4. Results

4.1. Quasistatic elastic loading

The results of the Young's moduli of the FT and SCNWs determined from the quasistatic loading simulations are shown in Fig. 2. The values have been normalized by the Young's modulus of the corresponding bulk crystal in the $\{110\}$ -direction ($E_{[110]}^{\text{free}}$) (see Tab. 1). To compare between the FT and the SCNWs, we introduce the diameter d^* , which is the equivalent diameter of a cylinder with cross sectional area of same magnitude. These diameters were normalized by the lattice constant a (see Tab. 1) to allow for a direct comparison of the different elements.

All SCNWs show an increase in Young's modulus with decreasing diameter, see Fig. 2a). The magnitude of this size effect however varies strongly for the different elements, and ranges from a very strong size effect for Au to nearly no size effect in the case of Ni. Power laws of the form $Ax^n + B$ have been fitted to the data points, the results are shown in the inset table and are plotted as dashed lines in Fig. 2a). With the exception of Ni, all exponents are close to $n = -1$, which is to be expected if the increase in size is linearly related to the surface to volume ratio which scales for the representative cylinder as d^{*-1} . The extrapolation for $d^*/a \rightarrow \infty$ yields $E_{[110]}^{\text{SC}}/E_{[110]}^{\text{free}} \rightarrow 1$ for all elements.

Figure 2: Size dependence of Young's moduli of simulated SC a) and FT b) NWs plotted over diameter of cylinder of same cross sectional area d^* normalized by the lattice constant. Inset table in a) shows parameters of fitted power law, which are plotted as dashed lines in a). Dashed lines in b) are guides to the eye connecting the single data points.

The situation is strikingly different for the case of the FTNWs shown in Fig. 2b). With increasing diameters, the Young's modulus $E_{[110]}^{\text{FT}}$ seems to level off at a constant value (between 1.05 and $1.1E_{[110]}^{\text{free}}$ for Au, Ni, Ag and Cu) rather than to converge to $E_{[110]}^{\text{free}}$ for $d^*/a \rightarrow \infty$. This suggests that the Young's modulus of FTNWs is fundamentally different from the Young's modulus of SCNWs, independent of diameter. Furthermore, dependent on the material, the Young's modulus can increase (Au, Cu) with decreasing wire diameters as well as decrease (Ag, Ni). Similar to the SCNWs the Young's modulus can also be nearly independent of diameter and close to the bulk value. However, in the SCNWs this is the case for Ni, in the FTNWs it is the case for Al. Close inspection of the values for the Cu FTNWs reveal that $E_{[110]}^{\text{FT}}$ first shows a slight decrease with decreasing diameter before it starts to increase below $d^* \leq 16a$. Consequently, the behavior of $E_{[110]}^{\text{FT}}$ as function of diameter can not be described by a simple power law, as in the case of the SCNWs.

In addition to the stress state at zero load, the stress state for Al and Ag FTNWs with diameter $d^* = 60a$ was also determined at 3% and 6% engineering strain, see Fig. 3. As can be seen from Fig. 3a) and b), the change in the values of the stress components is not homogenous throughout the wire: areas with higher stresses show larger changes in stress than the lower stressed areas closer to the surfaces. In the case of Ag (Fig. 3a)), the center of the wire where the disclination is located, shows an inversion in sign from highly compressive at zero strain over nearly zero stress to highly tensile at 6% strain. As the stress field is associated to the disclination in the center, this change in stress field would imply that the initially positive partial wedge disclination with $\omega = +7.35^\circ$ changes its Frank vector and ω becomes negative. The situation is however different in Al, see Fig. 3a). There, the most stressed areas show also the largest changes in stress, but the sign of the stress does not change between $\epsilon_{zz} = 0$ and 0.06.

4.2. Tensile tests at constant temperature and strain rate

The results of the simulated tensile tests at 300 K and a strain rate of $\dot{\epsilon} = 10^8 \text{ s}^{-1}$ of Ag and Al SCNWs and FTNWs ($d = 60a$, $l = 432a/\sqrt{2}$) are shown in Fig. 4 and Tab. 2. Movies of the tensile tests are available in the supplementary material (movies M1-M4). As

Figure 3: Illustration of stress inversion: a) and b) σ_{rr} and σ_{zz} for Ag and Al FTNWs ($d = 60a$) at different stages of uniaxial load showing the stress inversion in Ag FTNW occurring at about $\epsilon_{zz} = 0.03$ while there is no stress inversion for Al in that range, c) plot of $\omega(\epsilon_{zz})$ after equation 13 using Poisson ratios of the potentials.

Figure 4: a) Engineering stress-strain curves of tensile tests of FT and SC NWs ($d = 60a, l = 432a/\sqrt{2}a$) ; Ag b) and Al c) FTNWs at different stages of tensile test, colored according to centrosymmetry parameter (perfect fcc atoms are not shown), the pore formed in the Ag FTNW is indicated by the red arrow.

Table 2: Results of simulated tension and compression tests of nanowires ($d = 60a, l = 432a/\sqrt{2}$) at 300 K and a strain rate of 10^8 s^{-1} . Young’s modulus E , yield stress σ_y and strain at failure ϵ_f .

Sample	E / GPa	σ_y / GPa	ϵ_f /%
tension			
Ag FTNW	89.5	3.2	17
Ag SCNW	85.2	2.8	60
Al FTNM	80.6	3.0	19
Al SCNW	81.4	3.1	70
compression			
Ag FTNW	90.3	8.1	> 25
Ag SCNW	85.7	8.7	> 25

can be seen from the stress-strain curve, Fig. 4a), and Tab. 2, the differences between the Young’s moduli of the SCNWs and FTNWs observed in the MS simulations are still present in the MD simulations at 300 K. As typical for simulations of perfect, dislocation free NWs at the usual MD strain rates, all NWs show a high yield strength σ_y in the range of 2.8 to 3.2 GPa. The yield strength of the Ag FTNW is about 12 % higher than for the SCNW, for the Al FTNW however, σ_y is around 3 % smaller than that of the SCNW, see Tab. 2.

The onset of yielding is immediately followed by a sharp stress drop, which is followed by short increase in stress, after which the FTNWs rapidly fail, whereas the SCNWs deform at a stress level around 0.8 GPa and attain significant strains, see also Fig. S2 in the supplementary material. Before the onset of fracture, the flow stress of the FTNWs is larger than in the SCNWs. Again, this difference is more pronounced in Ag than in Al. The fracture strains of the SCNWs are about four times higher than for the FTNWs. This high ductility is caused by massive deformation twinning in both the Ag and Al SCNWs, see movies M2 and M4. This deformation mode of $\langle 110 \rangle$ -oriented fcc SCNWs has been thoroughly studied in the literature (Cao and Wei, 2006; Leach et al., 2007; Lee et al., 2014;

Park et al., 2006; Sedlmayr et al., 2012), and is therefore not further analyzed here.

In contrast, the FTNWs with the same orientation do not show massive deformation twinning - only a couple of 2-3 layer twins were observed, which were confined to their twin segments. Fig. 4b) and c) show configurations of the Ag and Al FTNWs after the onset of yielding and after fracture. In the case of the FTNWs the deformation is initiated by the nucleation at the surfaces of $\delta A(d)$ and $\alpha D(a)$ Shockley partial dislocations (Burgers vectors are given in the usual Thompson tetrahedron notation (Hirth and Lothe, 1982)). Transmission of these partial dislocations through the twin boundaries leads to fivefold symmetric arrangement of stacking faults. In some cases also the nucleation of trailing partial dislocations (e.g. $C\alpha(a)$ or $B\alpha(a)$) has been observed.

In both Ag and Al FTNWs, the deformation is localized in one region along the lengths of the FTNWs, while other regions stay in the perfect FT configuration. One striking difference between the two FTNWs is the formation of a pore in the Ag FTNW (indicated by the red arrow in Fig. 4). This pore formed during complex dislocation processes at or close to the quintuple line. No pore formation could be observed in the Al FTNW. The Ag FTNW finally fractures at the pore, which grew over the course of the tensile test leading to a particular fracture surface exhibiting a dimple. In contrast, only necking is observed in the case of the Al FTNW.

4.3. Compression tests

Dynamic compression tests at 300 K and a strain rate of 10^{-8} s^{-1} were carried out on Ag FT and SCNWs with diameter $d = 60a$ and length $l = 432a/\sqrt{2}$. The corresponding stress-strain curves are shown in Fig. 5a). The Young's moduli in compression are comparable to the ones in tension, see Tab. 2. However, the compressive strain causes a stiffening already for $\epsilon_{zz} < 1\%$, which explains the slightly increased Young's moduli compared to tension. For larger strains the stiffening increases further as can be seen in the increasing slope of the stress-strain curve, leading to overall higher stress values compared to the simulations of tensile tests, Fig. 4.

Both, the SC and the FTNW yield at a more than 2.5 times higher stress than under

Figure 5: Results of the compression tests: a) stress-strain curve for Ag FT and SCNWs ($d = 60a, l = 432a/\sqrt{2}a$); b) configuration of the SCNW and c) of the FTNW. Deformation is mainly caused by full dislocations leaving slip steps at the surfaces. In the FTNW additional extended partial dislocations on planes parallel to the compression axis are present (color coding according to the centrosymmetry parameter, only non-fcc atoms are shown).

tensile loading. This large difference can be understood by considering that the Schmid factor for the leading partial dislocation is a factor of two larger under tension than in compression, leading to lower tensile stresses required to nucleate dislocations under tension compared to compression (Lee et al., 2014). In contrast to the simulated tensile tests, the FTNW has a *lower* yield stress than the SCNW, compare Fig. 4 and Tab. 2.

The deformation is in both cases carried by full dislocations, as can be seen by the slip steps and the bounded stacking faults in Fig. 5b). This is in accordance to the larger resolved shear stress on the trailing compared to the leading partial dislocation under compression (Lee et al., 2014). A peculiarity of the FTNW under compression is the occurrence of full dislocations as well as extended stacking faults on glide planes parallel to the twin planes ((*b*) or (*c*)-planes), see Figs. 5c)). These dislocations either nucleate directly at the surface or cross-slip from the (*a*) and (*d*)-planes onto the (*b*) or (*c*)-planes. It is important to note that dislocations on these glide planes do not contribute to the longitudinal deformation of the wire under the compressive load.

5. Discussion

5.1. Stress state of fivefold twinned nanowires

The atomic stresses in the cross section of an Ag FTNW are compared in Fig. 6 to the stress state around a $\omega = 7.35^\circ$ wedge disclination according to Eqs. 1 - 4. In these isotropic solutions, the Voigt average of the elastic constants of the Ag potential were used, leading to $\mu = 33.9$ GPa and $\nu = 0.35$. As can be seen in Fig. 6, the stress state of the Ag FTNWs compares well to the analytically expected stress state of a wedge disclination in an isotropic material, both qualitatively and quantitatively. Both feature the highly compressive stress state at the center of the NW, where the disclination is located. The stress components σ_{rr} , $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$ and σ_{zz} show a radial symmetric distribution with deviations at the twin boundaries in the simulation results. Qualitatively, the overall stress state is similar for the different potentials, and shows no significant change with diameter.

A significant difference is the occurrence of a nonzero $\sigma_{r\theta}$ in the MS simulations, which would be expected to be zero according to the analytical solution, Eq. 4. The magnitude of

Figure 6: Comparison of a) the stress state in the cross section of the relaxed Ag NW ($d = 60a$) and b) the analytical solution of the stress field of a wedge disclination ($\omega = 7.35^\circ$) at the center of a disk of isotropic material with elastic properties according to a Voigt average of the elastic constants of the Ag potential ($\mu = 33.9$ GPa, $\nu = 0.35$). The respective $\sigma_{ij} = 0$ level is plotted as black contour line.

$\sigma_{r\theta}$ is maximal at the intersection of the twin boundaries with the free surface, and has opposite signs in the adjoining crystallites. Corresponding shear strains $\epsilon_{r\theta}$ were also observed by Johnson et al. (2007) in HRTEM studies of a FT Au nanoparticle. The observed shear stresses are a direct consequence of the elastic anisotropy of the material and are therefore not captured by the isotropic elastic solution. At the twin boundaries, the crystallographic orientation changes, and so does the elastic response. However, at coherent interfaces like twin boundaries, displacements and strains parallel to the interface have to be continuous across the boundary (Sutton and Balluffi, 1995).

Therefore, compatibility stresses arise at the twin boundaries to compensate the different elastic responses of the twin segments due to the strain caused by the gap closure (which corresponds the presence of the wedge disclination).

Although the presence of twin boundaries, free surfaces and anisotropic elasticity leads to deviations from the analytical isotropic solutions, Fig. 6 shows that disclination theory is useful to describe the stress and strain state in FTNWs.

5.2. Elastic response of fivefold twinned nanostructures:

a simple analytical model and complementary finite element analysis

For a single crystalline material, the Young's modulus in a certain direction can be determined from anisotropic elasticity theory, in which Hook's law takes the form (Hirth and Lothe, 1982)

$$\sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl}\epsilon_{kl} , \quad (5)$$

where σ_{ij} denotes the components of the stress tensor, C_{ijkl} represents the components of the tensor of elastic constants and ϵ_{kl} are the components of the strain tensor. As usual, the Einstein sum convention is used in the index notation of Hook's law, Eq. 5. The stresses and strains of interest here are described in the primed coordinate system shown in Fig. 1b) with axis $\mathbf{x}' = [10\bar{1}]$, $\mathbf{y}' = [010]$, $\mathbf{z}' = [101]$. The tensor of elastic constants in this coordinate system thus reads

$$C'_{ijkl} = M_{im}M_{jn}M_{ko}M_{lp}C_{mnop} , \quad (6)$$

with the rotation matrix

$$M_{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

Using the Voigt notation (Hirth and Lothe, 1982) and the fact that cubic materials only have three independent elastic constants C_{11} , C_{12} , C_{44} , the stress tensor in the primed coordinate system for an arbitrary strain tensor can be calculated to

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma'_{xx} \\ \sigma'_{yy} \\ \sigma'_{zz} \\ \sigma'_{yz} \\ \sigma'_{xz} \\ \sigma'_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\epsilon'_{xx}(C_{11}+C_{12}+2C_{44})}{2} + C_{12}\epsilon'_{yy} + \frac{\epsilon'_{zz}(C_{11}+C_{12}-2C_{44})}{2} \\ C_{12}\epsilon'_{xx} + C_{11}\epsilon'_{yy} + C_{12}\epsilon'_{zz} \\ \frac{\epsilon'_{xx}(C_{11}+C_{12}-2C_{44})}{2} + C_{12}\epsilon'_{yy} + \frac{\epsilon'_{zz}(C_{11}+C_{12}+2C_{44})}{2} \\ 2C_{44}\epsilon'_{yz} \\ \epsilon'_{xz}(C_{11} - C_{12}) \\ 2C_{44}\epsilon'_{xy} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

Under uniaxial strain in z -direction, a crystal in this orientation which can freely relax in the orthogonal directions will experience a tensile stress σ'_{zz} which can be calculated from Eq. 8 under the condition that $\sigma'_{xx} = \sigma'_{yy} = 0$. The constant relating stress and strain in this direction is the Young's modulus $E_{[101]}^{\text{free}} = \frac{\partial \sigma'_{zz}}{\partial \epsilon'_{zz}}$, which is that of a $[101]$ oriented single crystal without constraints :

$$E_{[101]}^{\text{free}} = \frac{4C_{44}(C_{11}^2 + C_{11}C_{12} - 2C_{12}^2)}{C_{11}^2 - 2C_{12}^2 + C_{11}(C_{12} + 2C_{44})} \quad (9)$$

The Poisson ratios in x - and y - direction for a crystal segment in the orientation of Fig. 1b) which is free to relax in the transversal directions ($\sigma'_{xx} = \sigma'_{yy} = 0$) while being deformed along the z -direction ($= [101]$) can be derived to

$$\nu_{[101]}^{[10\bar{1}]} = -\frac{\partial \epsilon'_{xx}}{\partial \epsilon'_{zz}} = \frac{-C_{11}^2 - C_{11}C_{12} + 2C_{12}^2 + 2C_{11}C_{44}}{-C_{11}^2 - C_{11}C_{12} + 2C_{12}^2 - 2C_{11}C_{44}}, \quad (10)$$

$$\nu_{[101]}^{[010]} = -\frac{\partial \epsilon'_{yy}}{\partial \epsilon'_{zz}} = \frac{4C_{12}C_{44}}{C_{11}^2 + C_{11}C_{12} - 2C_{12}^2 + 2C_{11}C_{44}}. \quad (11)$$

The Young's modulus and Poisson ratios for the various potentials used in this work are given in Tab. 1.

Figure 7: Young’s moduli determined by the simulations of the largest FT wires ($d = 122a$) normalized by the according Young’s modulus of the bulk crystal $E_{[101]}^{\text{free}}$ (Eq. 9) plotted over the anisotropy ratio A of the potential. Also shown are the results of FEM calculations and the analytical solution $E_{[101]}^{\text{constr.}}$ according to Eq. 12.

The increase in the Young’s moduli of FTNWs compared to SCNWs is related to the material’s elastic anisotropy ratio A , see Fig. 7. The larger A , the higher the value of $E_{[110]}^{\text{FT}}/E_{[101]}^{\text{free}}$. This can be easily understood: elastic anisotropy leads to different Poisson ratios in the directions orthogonal to the tensile axis (Eqs. 10 and 11 and Tab. 1). However, different lateral expansions would violate the *constraint of constant wedge angle* imposed by the FT structure. The effect of this compatibility constraint becomes more pronounced the larger A . The constraint that the angle α between the $\{111\}$ twin boundaries of each segment has to stay constant leads to the condition that the strain in x - and y -direction have to be equal ($\epsilon'_{xx} = \epsilon'_{yy}$). Assuming that crystal segments are able to relax in the y -direction (free surface, $\sigma'_{yy} = 0$), the Young’s modulus under this constraint, $E_{[101]}^{\text{constr.}}$, can be derived to

$$E_{[101]}^{\text{constr.}} = \frac{(C_{11} + 2C_{12})(C_{11} - C_{12} + 2C_{44})}{2(C_{11} + C_{12})}. \quad (12)$$

Comparing the Young’s moduli of FTNWs determined from simulations with $E_{[101]}^{\text{free}}$ from Eq. 9 (see also Tab. 1) in Fig. 7 shows that the overall trend of increasing $E_{[101]}^{\text{free}}$ with increasing A is captured by this simple expression. However, Eq. 9 underestimates the actual increase in Young’s moduli of FTNWs compared to the bulk single crystal value.

This indicates that the actual constraints in FTNWs are more complex. The segments do not deform independently of each other and compatibility stresses need to be taken into account.

To include the effects of the constraints due to the fivefold twined structure in more detail, finite element (FE) calculations were performed using cylindrical FTNWs and linear anisotropic elasticity with the values of the C_{ij} according to the EAM potentials, Tab. 1 (for detailed information about the FE calculations see the supplementary material). The so determined values for the Young's moduli are also shown in Fig. 7. As can be seen, the FE analysis consistently *overestimates* the increase in Young's moduli of FTNWs compared to the bulk value. However, as the FE analysis does not include non-linear elasticity, size effects or other atomistic effects, the calculations unequivocally show that the increase of the Young's modulus in FTNWs can be explained as a consequence of the geometrical constraints imposed by the five-fold twined microstructure. In contrast, the differences between the Young's moduli determined by the FE calculations and the atomistic calculations as well as their dependence on the wire diameter have to be of atomistic origin.

5.3. Atomic scale stress-strain response and size effects

The FTNWs as well as the SCNWs show a clear dependence of their Young's moduli on the wire diameter, see Fig. 2. Whereas FTNW show, depending on the material, decreasing as well as increasing Young's moduli with decreasing wire diameter, all SCNWs with the exception of Ni show an increase of the Young's modulus with decreasing diameter. This observation follows the trend described in the literature, e.g., for simulations of Cu (Liang et al., 2005) and Ag (McDowell et al., 2008b; Yoo et al., 2010) $\langle 110 \rangle$ -oriented single crystalline NWs. The size effect is commonly ascribed to the increase in the surface to volume ratio with decreasing diameter (Liang et al., 2005; McDowell et al., 2008a,b; Wu et al., 2011; Yoo et al., 2010). This is in agreement with our result that (with the exception of Ni) the increase of the Young's modulus is proportional to $(d^*)^n$ with $n \approx -1$ (see Fig. 2a)). The influence of the surface on the Young's modulus is commonly attributed to surface stresses (Liang et al., 2005): relaxation of these stresses leads to a shortening of the wire until the

compressive stress of the atoms inside the wire balances the surface stresses leading to a wire which, averaged over the cross section, is stress free. This results in initial compressive prestrain for the atoms inside the wire, which in turn is assumed to lead to an increase of the Young’s modulus due to nonlinear elastic effects (Liang et al., 2005). The general increase of the Young’s modulus with increasing compressive strain can also be directly evidenced in Fig. 5a).

Fig. 8a) shows that indeed the SCNWs shrink during relaxation. The increase in Young’s modulus is in turn linearly related to this prestrain, as shown in Fig. 8c). The situation is different in the FTNWs, where only wires with a small diameter shrink during relaxation, whereas relaxation leads to a *tensile* prestrain in the wires with larger diameters, see Fig. 8b). No general trend can be inferred for the dependence of the Young’s modulus of FTNWs on their prestrain. Depending on the material, decreasing as well as increasing or unchanged Young’s moduli are found, see Fig. 8c).

The effect of strain state on the Young’s modulus can also be directly determined by calculating the local tensor of elastic constants from the second order partial derivatives of the potential energy of the atoms with respect to the interatomic distances and the local atomic volume, see e.g. (Alber et al., 1992). Within the EAM formalism, these derivatives can be obtained by numerical differentiation of the potential functions. The local atomic volume required for the calculation of the local elastic constants is determined by a Voronoi tessellation. The “local Young’s modulus” in [101] direction is then taken as the inverse of the component S_{11} of the full compliance tensor in the appropriate coordinate system. Fig. 9a) shows that when the length of the Ag SCNW is held constant according to the equilibrium lattice parameter, the local Young’s modulus is rather homogeneous through the wire cross section and its average fits nicely the calculated value of 83.8 GPa for bulk Ag (see Tab. 1). When the axial stress due to the surface stresses is allowed to relax, the length of the wire decreases by 1% and the local Young’s moduli increase to an average of $\bar{E}_{\text{local}} = 84.9$ GPa (Fig. 9a), right). This value is slightly larger than the Young’s modulus determined from the quasistatic tensile test of this wire $E = 84.1$ GPa.

The calculation of the local elastic constants of the Ag FTNW however shows a significant

Figure 8: Prestrain along the wire axis induced during the relaxation of SCNWs a) and FTNWs b) as function of their diameter d^* ; c) relative change of the Young's modulus of SCNWs and FTNWs compared to the bulk value as function of the prestrain induced during relaxation.

Figure 9: Local Young's modulus determined from the local elastic constants for the Ag FTNW a) and the SCNW b) with the largest diameter. Left: relaxed configuration without box relaxation, right: with stress relaxation in axial direction. Stress relaxation leads in the case of the SCNW to a compressive strain and an increase of E . For the FTNW, relaxation of axial stresses leads to a tensile strain and a decrease of E ; c) shows the normalized Young's moduli of Ag and Ni SCNWs as function of their diameter as determined by the quasistatic tensile test and by averaging over the local elastic constants.

reduction of the local Young’s modulus: when the stress along the wire axis is allowed to relax, the wire length increases by 2.7% and the average local Young’s modulus decreases to $\bar{E}_{\text{local}} = 70.1$ GPa, see Fig. 9b), which is much smaller than the Young’s modulus determined from the quasistatic tensile test of this wire $E = 90.8$ GPa. The decreased averaged local Young’s modulus can be explained by the Poisson’s ratio derived in Eq. 10: Closure of the 7.35° gap in the FT structure (see Fig. 1b)) requires a tensile strain in $[10\bar{1}]$ -direction (leading to the tensile stress $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$ in shown in Fig. 6), which according to Eq. 10 in turn induces tensile strain in the axial $[101]$ -direction. As a compressive strain leads to an increase in Young’s modulus due to nonlinear elastic effects (Liang et al., 2005), a tensile strain should correspondingly lead to its decrease.

The local Young’s modulus (Fig. 9b)) clearly shows that contrary to SCNWs the increase in Young’s modulus in axial direction in FTNWs is *not* due to the strain state of the atoms inside the wires. This is in contrast to the work of Yoo et al. (2010), who found a locally increased elastic modulus in FTNW. Their calculation of the local Young’s modulus is however based on applying a tensile strain on the wire and fitting a second order polynomial to the virial stress - global strain curve. By this approach, the stress field due to the disclination gets mixed into the calculations, and the result does therefore not correspond to a local Young’s modulus.

The change in the local Young’s modulus due to the strain state is however not the only atomistic effect. Fig. 9c) compares the increase of the Young’s modulus as determined from the quasistatic tensile test to the average of the local Young’s modulus of Ag and Ni SCNWs. It can be seen that the average local Young’s modulus \bar{E}_{local} is always larger than the Young’s modulus determined by the tensile tests. The calculation of \bar{E}_{local} however does not include surface atoms, as their local volume can not be defined by a Voronoi tessellation. Consequently, the difference between \bar{E}_{local} and the Young’s modulus determined from tensile test must be caused by significantly lower contribution to the elastic response from the surface atoms. This is in agreement with the observation of Liang et al. (2005) that “the nanowire surface is always softer than the (equivalent) bulk” and the mostly negative values of the surface elastic modulus tensor as determined by Shenoy (2005). Fig. 9c) shows that like

in the case of Ni, the influence of the surface elastic modulus can be so large that it offsets the increase of the local Young’s modulus due to the surface-stress induced compressive prestrain (Fig. 8).

Whereas the increase of the Young’s modulus of SCNWs is solely caused by atomistic effects, namely the surface stress and the surface stiffness, the size-dependence of the elastic response of FTNWs is more complex. The constraints by the fivefold twinned structure lead to a size-independent increased apparent Young’s modulus, but also to a decrease in the local elastic constants. The surface stress and surface stiffness effects are similar to the SCNWs, although with different magnitudes, as the FTNWs possess only $\{100\}$ surfaces compared to the $\{111\}$ and $\{100\}$ surfaces of the SCNWs. The compression of the wire by the surface stresses has to act against the tensile prestrain due to the fivefold twinned structure, so that only the wires with very small diameters experience compressive strains along the wire axis. Whether the increase in local elastic constants due to these compressive strains can lead to a further increase in the Young’s modulus then depends on the magnitude of the surface stiffness. Our results clearly show that although the size dependent elastic modulus of FTNWs might in some cases be described by a purely empirical core-shell composite structure model (Zheng et al., 2014), such a model can not be generally applied to FTNWs and does not capture the underlying physics.

5.4. Influence of anisotropic elasticity on the plastic deformation in fivefold twinned nanowires

The example of the Ag FTNW shown in Fig. 3a) demonstrates that with increasing tensile strain an inversion of the stress state in σ_{rr} and σ_{zz} from compressive to tensile can occur close to the quintuple line of FTNWs. This stress inversion corresponds to a change in the sign of the Frank vector of the central partial wedge disclination. The framework developed in section 5.2 can be used to explain this phenomenon. Due to the elastic anisotropy, the Poisson ratios are different in the $[10\bar{1}]$ and the $[010]$ directions, leading to a contraction of the segments in the direction of the surface normals and an expansion orthogonal to the surface normal and the wire axis. This changes the angle α in Fig. 1b) and thus the misfit $2\pi - 5\alpha$ between the twin segments which has to be compensated by the partial wedge

disclination. The magnitude of the partial wedge disclination ω can therefore be expressed via the transversal Poisson ratios as function of the applied uniaxial strain ϵ_{zz} as

$$\omega(\epsilon_{zz}) = 2\pi - 10 \arctan \left(\frac{1 - \nu_{[10\bar{1}]}^{[10\bar{1}]} \epsilon_{zz}}{\sqrt{2} \left(1 - \nu_{[101]}^{[010]} \epsilon_{zz} \right)} \right). \quad (13)$$

This function is plotted in Fig. 3c), using the Poisson ratios calculated from the elastic constants of the potentials according to equations 10 and 11 (see Tab. 1 for the numerical values). Stress inversion takes place when the Frank vector of the partial disclination is zero, i.e., $\omega(\epsilon_{zz}) = 0$, which corresponds to a wedge angle of the segments of exactly $\alpha = 72^\circ$. The strain $\epsilon_{zz}(\omega = 0)$ for which this is expected to take place is provided in Tab. 1. As shown in Fig. 3, the observed stress inversion in Ag at $\epsilon_{zz} = 0.03$ agrees well with $\epsilon_{zz}(\omega = 0) = 0.029$ predicted by Eq. 13. For Al, no similar inversion is observed in the range of $\epsilon_{zz} = 0 - 0.06$, which agrees with the much larger elastic strain of $\epsilon_{zz}(\omega = 0) = 0.19$ required according to Eq. 13 for the central partial disclination to vanish.

The stress state of a uniaxially strained wire containing a partial wedge disclination along its axis therefore does *not* correspond to a superposition of a homogeneous uniaxial stress and the stress field of the disclination at zero applied strain. Instead the stress field of the disclination with an elastic *strain dependent Frank vector* according to Eq. 13 needs to be taken into account in determining the overall stress state.

The uniaxial tension and compression tests demonstrate clearly the importance of the strain-dependent stress field of the disclination on the plastic deformation: under tension, the Ag wire which shows a inversion from compressive to tensile stresses at the quintuple line fails by void formation whereas the Al FTNW without such stress inversion fails by necking (Figs. 3 and 4); under compression, dislocations do not only glide on the slip system with the highest Schmid factor, but form structural dislocations on glide planes with zero Schmid factor to relieve the increasing stress field of the disclination (Fig. 5). Predicting the activity of a certain slip system in FTNWs requires therefore the calculation of the resolved shear stress τ from the entire stress tensor, including the strain-state dependent stress due to the disclination, and not just the Schmid factor. Fig. 10b) shows such a calculation of τ

for the structural partial dislocation $C\beta(b)$ leading to the extended stacking faults visible in Figs 5c) and 10a). At $\epsilon_{zz} = 0.03$ the resolved shear stress vanishes, because the magnitude of the disclination in Ag FTNWs becomes negligible as shown above. At equilibrium $\epsilon_{zz} = 0$ there is a notable resolved shear stress on the partial dislocation which increases dramatically when the wire is compressed to $\epsilon_{zz} = -0.03$.

So far, under tension only increased yield strengths of FTNWs compared to SCNWs were reported in the literature of atomistic simulations of Cu, Ag and Pt wires (Cao and Wei, 2006; Gao et al., 2012; Leach et al., 2007; Sun et al., 2013b; Wen et al., 2012). Fig. 4 and Tab. 2 show a similar increase in yield strength for the Ag FTNW ($d = 60a$) under tension. Our simulations however demonstrate clearly that the fivefold twinned structure does not automatically lead to a strengthening of the wire: the Al FTNW shows a small decrease of σ_y^{FT} when compared to σ_y^{SC} and under compression the Ag FTNW has a 7% lower yield strength than the SCNW, see Tab. 2.

The increased yield strength is commonly attributed in the literature to the enhanced stiffness of the FTNWs (Leach et al., 2007; Wen et al., 2012) and the fact that dislocation nucleation from corners is prevented by the internal twin boundaries (Cao and Wei, 2006; Gao et al., 2012; Leach et al., 2007). However, it is evident from our simulations that in addition the strain-dependent stress field at the nucleation site due to the disclination has to be also taken into account. This is of particular importance as the tensile stress is with increasing strain not homogeneously increasing across the wire. This is shown in Fig. 3a) and b). In the case of Ag, the increase of σ_{zz} is more pronounced in the center of the wire than at the surfaces, whereas in Al it is the other way around, and the stress is increased at the surface where the dislocations nucleate. Under compression also structural dislocations form in the FTNW, therefore the von Mises stress is shown in Fig. 10c) for the Ag FT and SCNWs. Under tension, the von Mises stress in the FTNW is only slightly increased close to the center of the $\{100\}$ surfaces compared to the overall stress state in the SCNW. Under compression, however, the von Mises stress in the FTNW is locally much higher than in the SCNW.

The difference in yield stress between the SCNWs and FTNWs should therefore in general

Figure 10: a) Configuration of Ag FTNW at 6% compression with structural dislocations indicated by red arrows. Atoms are colored according to centrosymmetry parameter (perfect fcc atoms not shown). The inset shows the orientation of Thompson tetrahedra of the segments of the multiply twinned geometry used in the notation, b) resolved shear stress acting on the $C\beta$ partial dislocations in dependence of ϵ_{zz} , c) von Mises stress within Ag FT and SCNW ($d = 60a$) for 5% compression (left) and 5% tension (right) (static simulation, surface atoms have been removed).

depend in a non-trivial way on the specific material and the shape of the wire. E.g., on the differences in the energy barrier to nucleate dislocations from different surfaces versus edges, and via Eqs. 13 and 1 - 4 on the elastic constants and elastic anisotropy, which determine the stress state of the disclination containing wire.

5.5. Relationship to experiments

At the time of writing, only tensile tests on Ag FTNWs were reported in the literature, without direct comparison to SCNWs (Filleter et al., 2012; Zhu et al., 2012). The large increase of the Young's modulus by 50-80 % for wire diameters of the order of 40 nm reported by Zhu et al. (2012) and Filleter et al. (2012) is not found in our simulations, where wires of similar diameter show only an increase of about 8 %. The uncertainty in Young's modulus might possibly be attributed to errors, e.g. in the determination of the cross sectional area in the experiments. However, Filleter et al. (2012) performed a careful error analysis, which included the effect of the carbon coating layer and determined their systematic error to be about 20 %.

Atomistic simulations have their own sets of limitations like the small scales and short times which can be simulated. In particular, the results depend critically on the quality of the used potentials. Although EAM potentials are fitted to the surface energies, surface stress and stiffness are usually not considered in the development of potentials. They might therefore fail to quantitatively reproduce the size effect in elastic properties of nanowires. However, the analytical framework developed to explain the size independent differences in Young's modulus between FTNWs and SCNWs and the strain dependent Frank vector is solely based on linear anisotropic elasticity. Predictions based on this model should therefore be independent of the details of the potentials and experimentally testable.

Currently, only increased Young's moduli compared to single crystals have been reported in the literature (Filleter et al., 2012; McDowell et al., 2008b; Sun et al., 2013b; Wen et al., 2012; Wu et al., 2011; Yoo et al., 2010; Zheng et al., 2014; Zhu et al., 2012). However, for materials with low anisotropy ratio, A , like aluminum our model predicts a decreased Young's module for (large) FTNWs. Al FTNWs have not been reported in the literature, but

Platinum FT nanorods exist (Hofmeister, 2004). According to its elastic constants ($C_{11} = 346.7$ GPa, $C_{12} = 250.7$ GPa, $C_{44} = 76.5$ GPa, $A = 1.6$ (Macfarlane and Rayne, 1965)), our model would predict a significant decrease of the Young's modulus from $E_{[101]}^{\text{free}} = 185.3$ GPa to $E_{[101]}^{\text{constr.}} = 176.7$ GPa for Pt FTNW. This prediction deviates from the enhanced Young's modulus of FTNWs compared to SCNWs found in the atomistic simulations of Wen et al. (2012). However, taking into account the size effect on the Young's modulus, Fig. 2, the diameters of the NWs used in their study ($d = 4$ nm) do not allow to discuss the fundamental, size-independent differences in elastic behavior between FTNWs and SCNWs.

The formation of voids under tension as observed in our simulations of Ag FTNWs was not reported by Filleter et al. (2012). However, their FTNWs yielded at strains of the order of 3%, just about the strain where according to our calculations the stress inversion should take place (Fig. 3c). Experiments on FTNWs with better surface quality and a lower misalignment angle might be able to achieve larger elastic strains and thus show void formation. Alternatively, materials with higher anisotropy ratio which should show a stress inversion at lower strains could be used to test the hypothesis of stress inversion in FTNWs upon tension.

6. Outlook

The unique microstructure of FTNWs opens up new routes for strain-engineering of materials properties (Li et al., 2014). For example by alloying with elements which segregate to the compressive strain field of the disclination, changes of the disclination stress field with tensile strain would require more energy, thereby additionally stiffening the wire. In semiconductors, the large strains at the disclination core could furthermore lead to different band gaps in the wire centre compared to the outer wire. The leverage effect of the joined twins, which, due to the anisotropy in the Poisson expansion amplifies the effect of uniaxial strain in the middle of the wire, would allow for a highly sensitive tuning of the electronic and opto-electronic properties of such wires.

7. Summary

In summary, we have presented the results of atomistic simulations of the stress-strain response of Ag, Al, Au, Cu and Ni [110]-oriented fivefold twinned and single crystalline nanowires with diameters between 2 and 50 nm. Whereas the single crystalline nanowires show an increase of the Young's modulus compared to a bulk crystal of identical orientation, the situation is more complex in the case of fivefold twinned nanowires: for large diameters all materials show an increased Young's modulus independent of the diameter, whereas for smaller diameters, depending on the material, decreasing as well as increasing Young's moduli were observed. Furthermore, under tensile load Ag fivefold twinned nanowires show an increased yield strength compared to their single crystalline counterparts and fail by formation and growth of pores in the center of the wire, whereas the fivefold twinned Al nanowires show a decrease in yield stress and fail by necking. Under compression, the fivefold twinned Ag nanowire however shows a lower yield stress compared to the corresponding single crystalline wire.

The differences in Young's moduli can be rationalized by taking into account the compatibility constraint imposed by the fivefold twinned structure and the anisotropy in Poisson contraction on top of the size effects due to surface stresses and surface stiffness. The anisotropy in Poisson contraction can be used to calculate the strength of the central partial wedge disclination, i.e., its Frank vector, as function of uniaxial strain. The plastic deformation of fivefold twinned structures depends critically on the local stress field which is a combination of the applied stress and the strain-dependent stress field of the disclination. Depending on the elastic anisotropy, this can lead to a stress-inversion from compressive to tensile stress in the center of the fivefold twinned wires under tensile load, causing the pore formation observed in the fivefold twinned Ag nanowire, to an increased or decreased yield stress compared to single crystalline nanowires, depending on the elastic anisotropy of the material and the loading direction, as well as to the formation of structural dislocations under compression.

The framework of constraint anisotropic elasticity in fivefold twinned nanowires devel-

oped in this paper allows to calculate the stress state within these wires as function of applied strain, and thus to predict their plastic response. In anisotropic elastic materials, the fivefold twinned structure acts as a lever by which one can control the stress state within nanowires by the application of external strain, thus opening up new possibilities for strain-engineering of materials properties.

Acknowledgements

This work has been financially supported by the DFG via the research training group 1896 “In Situ Microscopy with Electrons, X-rays and Scanning Probes” and the Cluster of Excellence EXC 315 “Engineering of Advanced Materials” (EAM). Computational resources have been provided by RRZE. F.N. thanks J. Li and his group (Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge) for fruitful discussions and W.G. Nöhring for providing his program to calculate resolved shear stresses.

References

- Alber, I., Bassani, J. L., Khantha, M., Vitek, V., Wang, G. J., 1992. Grain boundaries as heterogeneous systems: Atomic and continuum elastic properties. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. Lond. A* 339, 555–586.
- Allen, M. P., Tildesley, D. J., 1987. *Computer simulation of liquids*. Clarendon Pr., Oxford.
- Amodeo, J., Begau, C., Bitzek, E., 2014. Atomistic simulations of compression tests on ni₃al nanocubes. *Mater. Res. Lett.* 2, 140–145.
- Bitzek, E., Koskinen, P., Gähler, F., Moseler, M., Gumbsch, P., 2006. Structural relaxation made simple. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 997, 170201.
- Cao, A., Wei, Y., 2006. Atomistic simulations of the mechanical behavior of fivefold twinned nanowires. *Phys. Rev. B* 74, 214108.
- Chen, H., Gao, Y., Yu, H., Zhang, H., Liu, L., Shi, Y., Tian, H., Xie, S., Li, J., 2004a. Structural properties of silver nanorods with fivefold symmetry. *Micron* 35, 469–474.
- Chen, H., Gao, Y., Zhang, H., Liu, L., Yu, H., Tian, H., Xie, S., Li, J., 2004b. Transmission-electron-microscopy study on fivefold twinned silver nanorods. *J. Phys. Chem. B* 108, 12038–12043.
- Chen, L. Y., Richter, G., Sullivan, J. P., Gianola, D. S., 2012. Lattice anharmonicity in defect-free pd nanowhiskers. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 109, 125503.
- Damm, C., Segets, D., Yang, G., Vieweg, B., Spiecker, E., Peukert, W., 2011. Shape transformation mechanism of silver nanorods in aqueous solution. *Small* 7, 147–156.

- De Wit, R., 1972. Partial disclinations. *J. Phys. C: Solid State Phys.* 5, 529–534.
- Diao, J., Gall, K., Dunn, M. L., 2004. Atomistic simulation of the structure and elastic properties of gold nanowires. *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* 52, 1935–1962.
- Dingreville, R., Qu, J., Cherkaoui, M., 2005. Surface free energy and its effect on the elastic behavior of nano-sized particles, wires and films. *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* 53, 1827–1854.
- Filleter, T., Ryu, S., Kang, K., Yin, J., Bernal, R. A., Sohn, K., Li, S., Huang, J., Cai, W., Espinosa, H. D., 2012. Nucleation-controlled distributed plasticity in penta-twinned silver nanowires. *Small* 8, 2986–2993.
- Gao, Y., Fu, Y., Sun, W., Sun, Y., Wang, H., Wang, F., Zhao, J., 2012. Investigation on the mechanical behavior of fivefold twinned silver nanowires. *Comput. Mater. Sci.* 55, 322–328.
- Gao, Y., Song, L., Jiang, P., Liu, L., Yan, X., Zhou, Z., Liu, D., Wang, J., Yuan, H., Zhang, Z., Zhao, X., Dou, X., Zhou, W., Wang, G., Xie, S., Chen, H., Li, J., 2005. Silver nanowires with five-fold symmetric cross-section. *J. Cryst. Growth* 276, 606–612.
- Garnett, E., Cai, W., Cha, J., Mahmood, F., Connor, S., Christoforo, M., Cui, Y., McGehee, M., Brongersma, M., 2012. Self-limited plasmonic welding of silver nanowire junctions. *Nat. Mater.* 11, 241–249.
- Greer, J. R., Hosson, J. T. D., 2011. Plasticity in small-sized metallic systems: Intrinsic versus extrinsic size effect. *Prog. Mater. Sci.* 56, 654 – 724.
- Gryaznov, V. G., Heydenreich, J., Kaprelov, A. M., Nepijko, S. A., Romanov, A. E., Urban, J., 1999. Pentagonal symmetry and disclinations in small particles. *Cryst. Res. Technol.* 34, 1091–1119.
- Hirth, J. P., Lothe, J., 1982. *Theory of Dislocations*, 2nd Edition. John Wiley & Sons, New York.
- Hofmeister, H., 2004. Fivefold twinned nanoparticles. In: Nalwa, H. S. (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology*. Vol. 3. American Scientific Publishers, pp. 431–452.
- Hoover, W. G., 1985. Canonical dynamics equilibrium and phase-space distributions. *Phys. Rev. A* 31, 1695–1697.
- Hu, L., Kim, H. S., Lee, J.-Y., Peumans, P., Cui, Y., 2010. Scalable coating and properties of transparent, flexible, silver nanowire electrodes. *ACS Nano* 4, 2955–2963.
- Huang, R., Wen, Y.-H., Zhu, Z.-Z., Sun, S.-G., 2011. Thermal stability of platinum nanowires: a comparison study between single-crystalline and twinned structures. *J. Mater. Chem.* 21, 18998–19004.
- Jiang, S., Shen, Y., Zheng, Y., Chen, Z., 2013. Formation of quasi-icosahedral structures with multi-conjoint fivefold deformation twins in fivefold twinned metallic nanowires. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 103, 041909.
- Jing, G. Y., Duan, H. L., Sun, X. M., Zhang, Z. S., Xu, J., Li, Y. D., Wang, J. X., Yu, D. P., 2006. Surface effects on elastic properties of silver nanowires: Contact atomic-force microscopy. *Phys. Rev. B* 73, 235409.
- Johnson, C. L., Snoeck, E., Ezcurdia, M., Rodríguez-González, B., Pastoriza-Santos, I., Liz-Marzán, L. M.,

- Hýtch, M. J., 2007. Effects of elastic anisotropy on strain distributions in decahedral gold nanoparticles. *Nat. Mater.* 7, 120–124.
- Kolesnikova, A. L., Romanov, A. E., 2007. Stress relaxation in pentagonal whiskers. *Tech. Phys. Lett.* 33, 886–888.
- Kraft, O., Gruber, P. A., Mönig, R., Weygand, D., 2010. Plasticity in confined dimensions. *Annu. Rev. Mater. Res.* 40, 293–317.
- Krantz, J., Richter, M., Spallek, S., Spiecker, E., Brabec, C., 2011. Solution-processed metallic nanowire electrodes as indium tin oxide replacement for thin-film solar cells. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 21, 4784–4787.
- Krantz, J., Stubhan, T., Richter, M., Spallek, S., Litzov, I., Matt, G., Spiecker, E., Brabec, C., 2012. Spray-coated silver nanowires as top electrode layer in semitransparent p3ht:pcbm-based organic solar cell devices. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 23, 1711–1717.
- Leach, A. M., McDowell, M., Gall, K., 2007. Deformation of top-down and bottom-up silver nanowires. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 17, 43–53.
- Lee, J.-Y., Connor, S. T., Ciu, Y., Peumans, P., 2008. Solution-processed metal nanowire mesh transparent electrodes. *Nano Lett.* 8, 689–692.
- Lee, S., Im, J., Yoo, Y., Bitzek, E., Kiener, D., Richter, G., Kim, B., Oh, S. H., 2014. Reversible cyclic deformation mechanism of gold nanowires by twinning-detwinning transition evidenced from in situ tem. *Nat. Commun.* 5, 4033.
- Li, J., 2003. Atomeye: an efficient atomistic configuration viewer. *Modell. Simul. Mater. Sci. Eng.* 11, 173–177.
- Li, J., Shan, Z., Ma, E., 2014. Elastic strain engineering for unprecedented materials properties. *MRS Bull.* 39, 108–114.
- Liang, H., Upmanyu, M., Huang, H., 2005. Size-dependent elasticity of nanowires: Nonlinear effects. *Phys. Rev. B* 71, 241403.
- Lim, J.-W., Cho, D.-Y., Eun, K., Choa, S.-H., Na, S.-I., Kim, J., Kim, H.-K., 2012. Mechanical integrity of flexible ag nanowire network electrodes coated on colorless pi substrates for flexible organic solar cells. *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells* 105, 69–76.
- Lucas, M., Leach, A. M., McDowell, M. T., Hunyadi, S. E., Gall, K., Murphy, C. J., Riedo, E., 2008. Plastic deformation of pentagonal silver nanowires: Comparison between afm nanoindentation and atomistic simulations. *Phys. Rev. B* 77, 245420.
- Macfarlane, R. E., Rayne, J. A., 1965. Anomalous temperature dependence of shear modulus c_{44} for platinum. *Phys. Lett.* 18, 91–92.
- McDowell, M. T., Leach, A. M., Gall, K., 2008a. Bending and tensile deformation of metallic nanowires. *Modell. Simul. Mater. Sci. Eng.* 16, 045003.

- McDowell, M. T., Leach, A. M., Gall, K., 2008b. On the elastic modulus of metallic nanowires. *Nano Lett.* 8, 3613–3618.
- Miller, R. E., Shenoy, V. B., 2000. Size-dependent elastic properties of nanosized structural elements. *Nanotechnology* 11, 139–147.
- Mishin, Y., 2004. Atomistic modeling of the γ and γ' -phases of the Ni–Al system. *Acta Mater.* 52, 1451–1467.
- Mishin, Y., Farkas, D., Mehl, M. J., Papaconstantopoulos, D. A., 1999. Interatomic potentials for monoatomic metals from experimental data and ab initio calculations. *Phys. Rev. B* 59, 3393–3407.
- Mishin, Y., Mehl, M. J., Papaconstantopoulos, D. A., Voter, A. F., Kress, J. D., 2001. Structural stability and lattice defects in copper: Ab initio, tight-binding, and embedded-atom calculations. *Phys. Rev. B* 63, 224106.
- Monk, J., Hoyt, J. J., Farkas, D., 2008. Metastability of multitwinned ag nanorods: Molecular dynamics study. *Phys. Rev. B* 78, 024112.
- Ni, C., Hassan, P. A., Kaler, E. W., 2005. Structural characteristics and growth of pentagonal silver nanorods prepared by a surfactant method. *Langmuir* 21, 3334–3337.
- Niekiel, F., Bitzek, E., Spiecker, E., 2014. Combining atomistic simulation and x-ray diffraction for the characterization of nanostructures: A case study on fivefold twinned nanowires. *ACS Nano* 8, 1629–1638.
- Ogata, S., Li, J., Hirosaki, N., Shibutani, Y., Yip, S., 2004. Ideal shear strain of metals and ceramics. *Phys. Rev. B* 70, 104104.
- Oh, S., Legros, M., Kiener, D., Gruber, P., Dehm, G., 2007. In situ TEM straining of single crystal Au films on polyimide: Change of deformation mechanisms at the nanoscale. *Acta Mater.* 55, 5558–5571.
- Park, H. S., Gall, K., Zimmerman, J. A., 2006. Deformation of fcc nanowires by twinning and slip. *J. Mech. Phys. Solids* 54, 1862–1881.
- Park, H. S., Zimmerman, J. A., 2005. Modeling inelasticity and failure in gold nanowires. *Phys. Rev. B* 72, 054106.
- Reyes-Gasga, J., Elechiguerra, J., Liu, C., Camacho-Bragado, A., Montejano-Carrizales, J., Yacaman, M. J., 2006. On the structure of nanorods and nanowires with pentagonal cross-sections. *J. Cryst. Growth* 286, 162–172.
- Romanov, A. E., Polonsky, I. A. und Gryaznov, V. G., Nepijko, S. A., Junghanns, T., Vitrykhovski, N. I., 1993. Voids and channels in pentagonal crystals. *J. Cryst. Growth* 129, 691–698.
- Romanov, A. E., Vladimirov, V. I., 1992. Disclinations in crystalline solids. In: Nabarro, F. R. N. (Ed.), *Dislocations in Solids*. Vol. 9. North-Holland, Amsterdam, Ch. 47, pp. 191–402.
- Sandia National Laboratory, Kitware Inc., Los Alamos National Laboratory, 2000-2008. ParaView - Parallel Visualization Application. <http://www.paraview.org/>.
- Sedlmayr, A., Bitzek, E., Gianola, D. S., Richter, G., Mönig, R., Kraft, O., 2012. Existence of two twinning-

- mediated plastic deformation modes in au nanowhiskers. *Acta Mater.* 60, 3985–3993.
- Shankar, M. R., King, A. H., 2007. How surface stresses lead to size-dependent mechanics of tensile deformation in nanowires. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 90, 141907.
- Shenoy, V., 2005. Atomistic calculations of elastic properties of metallic fcc crystal surfaces. *Phys. Rev. B* 71, 094104.
- Shimizu, F., Ogata, S., Li, J., 2007. Theory of shear banding in metallic glasses and molecular dynamics calculations. *Mater. Trans.* 48, 2923–2927.
- Sun, M., Cao, R., Xiao, F., Deng, C., 2013a. Five-fold twin and surface groove-induced abnormal size- and temperature-dependent yielding in ag nanowires. *Scr. Mater.* 69, 227–230.
- Sun, M., Cao, R., Xiao, F., Deng, C., 2013b. Surface and interface controlled yielding and plasticity in fivefold twinned ag nanowires. *Comput. Mater. Sci.* 79, 289–295.
- Sutton, A. P., Balluffi, R. W., 1995. *Interfaces in Crystalline Materials*. Clarendon Press, Oxford.
- Weinberger, C. R., Cai, W., 2012. Plasticity of metal nanowires. *J. Mater. Chem.* 22, 3277–3292.
- Wen, Y.-H., Huang, R., Zhu, Z.-Z., Wang, Q., 2012. Mechanical properties of platinum nanowires: An atomistic investigation on single-crystalline and twinned structures. *Comput. Mater. Sci.* 55, 205–210.
- Williams, P. L., Mishin, Y., Hamilton, J. C., 2006. An embedded-atom potential for the cu–ag system. *Modell. Simul. Mater. Sci. Eng.* 14, 817–833.
- Wu, B., Heidelberg, A., Boland, J. J., 2005. Mechanical properties of ultrahigh-strength gold nanowires. *Nat. Mater.* 4, 525–529.
- Wu, B., Heidelberg, A., Boland, J. J., Sader, J. E., Sun, X., Li, Y., 2006. Microstructure-hardened silver nanowires. *Nano Lett.* 6, 468–472.
- Wu, J. Y., Nagao, S., He, J. Y., Zhang, Z. L., 2011. Role of five-fold twin boundary on the enhanced mechanical properties of fcc fe nanowires. *Nano Lett.* 11, 5264–5273.
- Yasnikov, I. S., Vikarchuk, A. A., 2007. Mechanisms of relaxation of elastic stresses in the process of growth of nanoparticles and microcrystals with disclination defects in electrocrystallization of fcc metals. *Met. Sci. Heat Treat.* 49, 97–104.
- Yoo, J. H., Oh, S. I., Jeong, M. S., 2010. The enhanced elastic modulus of nanowires associated with multitwins. *J. Appl. Phys.* 107, 094316.
- Zheng, Y. G., Zhao, Y. T., Ye, H. F., Zhang, H. W., 2014. Size-dependent elastic moduli and vibrational properties of fivefold twinned copper nanowires. *Nanotechnology* 25, 315701.
- Zhu, T., Li, J., 2010. Ultra-strength materials. *Prog. Mater. Sci.* 55, 710–757.
- Zhu, Y., Qin, Q., Xu, F., Fan, F., Ding, Y., Zhang, T., Wiley, B. J., Wang, Z. L., 2012. Size effects on elasticity, yielding, and fracture of silver nanowires: In situ experiments. *Phys. Rev. B* 85, 045443.

Supplementary Material for: Influence of anisotropic elasticity on the mechanical properties of fivefold twinned nanowires

Florian Niekel^a, Erdmann Spiecker^a, Erik Bitzek^{a,*}

^a*Department of Material Science and Engineering, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU), 91058 Erlangen, Germany*

1. Finite Element Calculations

The analytical model based on the constraint of a *constant wedge angle* does not take into account additional compatibility constraints or inhomogeneous stress/strain distribution within the twin segments. Therefore, finite element (FE) calculations have been performed utilizing anisotropic linear elasticity in *Abaqus 6.12*. The FTNWs have been modeled as cylinders (diameter 30 nm, length 20 nm) exhibiting a circular cross section subdivided into five segments with local orientation corresponding to that of fivefold twins. Symmetry boundary conditions have been utilized to simulate infinitely long NWs. 101590 hexahedral elements (C3D8R) have been used to mesh the structure with 10159 elements in the cross section and 10 subdivisions along the wire axis. The tensile test was simulated by stepwise displacement of one end for an engineering strain of up to 10 %. The anisotropic elastic constants of the EAM potentials used in the main work have been used as material parameters to allow a direct comparison of MS simulations, analytical model and FE calculations.

Fig. 1 shows the distribution of stress in wire axis direction σ_{zz} for a Ag FTNW at 10% tensile strain. As can be seen the stress distribution is homogeneous along the wire axis (due to the symmetry) but clearly inhomogeneous in the cross section. The elastic response

*Corresponding author. Address: Department of Material Science and Engineering, Intitute I: General Materials Properties, Martensstr. 5, 91058 Erlangen, Germany. Tel.: +49 9131 8527507, fax.: +49 9131 8527504.

Email address: erik.bitzek@fau.de (Erik Bitzek)

of the FTNWs has been quantified from the FE calculations determining the Young's modulus from the engineering stress-strain behavior. The strain has been determined from the applied displacement, the stress has been determined summing the forces on the nodes in the cross section and dividing it by the cross sectional area.

Tab. 1 summarizes the results of FE calculations using the different material parameters. The values have been plotted in comparison to the analytical model and MS simulations in Fig. 7 in the main manuscript. As discussed there, the FE calculations solely represent the impact of the geometrical constraint and does not include any effect due to size effect, prestrain and nonlinearity as well as surfaces or interfaces.

Figure 1: Finite element model of the FTNW showing the stress in tensile direction of a Ag FTNW at 10% tensile strain.

Table 1: Results on elastic response of FTNW from FE calculations, E_{zz}^{FEM} in GPa.

Element	E_{zz}^{FEM}
Ag	94.9
Al	80.1
Au	87.0
Cu	149.8
Ni	247.9

2. Tensile tests

Fig. 2 shows the engineering stress-strain curves of tensile tests of Ag and Al FT and SC NWs plotted up to the failure of the SCNWs.

Figure 2: Engineering stress-strain curves of tensile tests of FT and SC NWs ($d = 60a$, $l = 432a/\sqrt{2}$).

2.1. Movies

- M1.avi: MD simulation of tensile test of Ag FTNW ($d = 60a$, $l = 432a/\sqrt{2}$) at 300 K with a strain rate of 10^8 s^{-1} , colored according to centrosymmetry parameter (perfect fcc atoms not shown), engineering stress and strain have been annotated in the legend.

- M2.avi: MD simulation of tensile test of Ag SCNW ($d = 60a, l = 432a/\sqrt{2}$) at 300 K with a strain rate of 10^8 s^{-1} , colored according to centrosymmetry parameter (perfect fcc atoms not shown), engineering stress and strain have been annotated in the legend.
- M3.avi: MD simulation of tensile test of Al FTNW ($d = 60a, l = 432a/\sqrt{2}$) at 300 K with a strain rate of 10^8 s^{-1} , colored according to centrosymmetry parameter (perfect fcc atoms not shown), engineering stress and strain have been annotated in the legend.
- M4.avi: MD simulation of tensile test of Al SCNW ($d = 60a, l = 432a/\sqrt{2}$) at 300 K with a strain rate of 10^8 s^{-1} , colored according to centrosymmetry parameter (perfect fcc atoms not shown), engineering stress and strain have been annotated in the legend.